

StandICT.eu2029

Guidelines for Applicants to Fellowship StandICT.eu Open Calls

Funded by
the European Union

Introduction

This document provides the main guidelines for applicants who are interested in applying for StandICT.eu 2029 Open Calls.

In a series of six open calls, running until August 2027, StandICT.eu will provide € 4,200,000 of direct funding to support the participation of European standardisation specialists in key international and global Standards Development Organisations (SDOs).

The objective of the funding is to enable the specialists to contribute to and help create a fully integrated European Standardisation Ecosystem, thereby strengthening Europe's position in global standardisation initiatives.

A. Guidance for the Application Phase

1. Type of contributions

Applicants can request 3 different typologies of funding under the StandICT.eu 2029 Open Calls, as shown in the table below.

Typology	Description	Max duration	Max funding range per call
Long term contribution (LT)	Contribution to ongoing standards development as a chair, convener, rapporteur or member of an SDO WG. For example, commenting on standards development and drafts, attending meetings as an observer, and paying membership fees.	9 months	Up to 10.000 €
Short term contribution (ST)	Contribution to standards documentation e.g. liaison to WG, comments on standards drafts, participation at meeting paying membership fees	3 months	Up to 5.000 €
Organisation of Standardisation Meetings (SM)	Pilot type. Support to the organisation of strategic standardisation meetings in Europe, endorsed by an international SDO, global forum, or consortium. Eligible costs include venue and equipment rental, catering, communication materials, and travel and accommodation for key participants.	Max 6 months, depending on the scale and timing of the meeting	Up to 50.000 €

A third, pilot-type, proposal application has been introduced under this edition: the category regarding the **Organisation of Standardisation Meetings (SM)**, aimed at supporting the hosting of international standardisation meetings in Europe. In this particular funding typology, the maximum funding per application is set at 50.000€, and the same organisation may only be awarded once under this scheme for the duration of the project.

Both the maximum funding requested per proposal and the respective type of application (LT, ST, SM) cannot exceed that indicated.

Applications for SM calls are expected to start later than LT and ST calls.

For LT and ST Contributions, a total budget of approximately 4.000.000€ will be allocated.

For SM Contributions, a total budget of approximately 200.000€ will be allocated.

These are estimated amounts that will be better defined during the Open Calls process management, based on the topics and strategic needs of the project.

2. Process and timing of Open Call for Applications

StandICT.eu will run 6 Open Call cycles. Each call will be open for 60 days for proposal submission.

At the end of the sixty-day period all proposals received through [TRUST-GRANTS™](#) platform will be screened for eligibility, evaluated by an external pool of evaluators (EPE)¹, scored, and ranked for funding.

This process takes approximately 35 days, at the end of which all applicants shall be notified with the result of the evaluation process (e.g., retained fellowships or not successful application) and provided with access to a Consensus Report compiled by the EPE.

To guarantee maximum fairness and transparency, each application will be independently evaluated by three members of the EPE and will undergo quality control by a fourth member of the pool after consensus is reached.

As the EPE are highly-skilled experts whose qualifications are assessed through an open call process their decision is binding and any redress requests or complaints will be dealt with strictly in relation to the procedural aspects of the evaluation and not on the merits of scientific or technical judgement of the experts.

3. Criteria for receiving financial support

Applicants to LT and ST contributions must be **individuals or natural persons** residing in the European Member States and Associate Countries² from both public and private sectors, industry and service companies, including SMEs and start-ups, academia and research, and national and European associations, including NGOs representing consumer interests.

Applicants for SM contributions must be organisations based in a European Member State or Associated Country, with a demonstrable role in coordinating or supporting the organisation of meetings on behalf of international SDOs, global fora, or consortia.

Potential applicants are standardisation specialists, defined as professionals with proven expertise and experience in standardisation activities e.g. previous contributions to standards developments, participation in various SDO groups, previous or current chairs etc in the respective priority area. Also, European ICT experts willing to start their contribution to the standardisation working groups and/or technical committees are eligible even if they do not dispose of previous proven experience. For these experts, StandICT.eu offers support with a dedicated mentorship programme (see reference to the related section: [Mentorship programme](#)).

Applications from standardisation first-timers who are willing to increase their knowledge and experience in ICT standardisation activities are also welcomed. In this case, while filling in the application applicants can subscribe to the standICT.eu 2029 [Mentorship Programme](#), that pairs new SME experts who are less familiar with the workings of SDO technical committees with seasoned fellows for guidance and advice.

Applicants can apply to all StandICT.eu Open Calls, and can be funded for a maximum of 50k€ over this current edition of StandICT.eu which will end on 30 September 2028.

For **SM type of contributions**, the same organisation can only be awarded once, hence applying for a continuation of the previously funded activities is not permitted in this case.

For **LT and ST type of contributions**, applicants can also apply for a continuation of the previously funded activities, as long as they clearly demonstrate the progress made with respect to the previously funded application, the improvements that will be performed in the new activities and the different timeline of the new activities - the latter criteria is very important in order to avoid the suspicion of double funding. In particular, it is crucial to note that **applicants who copy and paste the same (even successfully funded) applications may risk being penalised**. While we strive to guarantee continuity to our fellowships, it must be crystal clear that the new application is a continuation, highlighting the main new aspects it will address.

In case of not funded activities, applicants can re-apply to the next open call and adjust the application according to the comments and suggestions made by the evaluators.

1 <https://standict.eu/call-external-evaluators>

2 https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/europe-world/international-cooperation/association-horizon-europe_en

In particular, the target of StandICT.eu open calls are European Experts who:

- ▣ have profound knowledge in one of the topics covered by the Open Calls;
- ▣ have experience regarding developments of standards, e.g., in SDOs, , in groups set-up by the EC, or when creating documentation in open source developments;
- ▣ are not receiving support from other instruments (PPPs, EU or national R&I projects) for the proposed activities, and are not being funded from other sources for an identical activity.

For the SM – Organisation of Standardisation Meetings proposal type, the target applicants are organisations based in a European Member State or Associated Country, with a demonstrable role in coordinating or supporting the organisation of meetings on behalf of international SDOs, global fora, or consortia. The proposed meetings must align with the objectives and thematic scope defined for each open call cycle. While co-funding from other sources is permitted, the activities supported by StandICT.eu 2029 must be clearly identified and not double-funded.

The most recent information listing participating countries in Horizon Europe issued by the Commission at the time of writing (25/07/2023) can be consulted here EU Grants: [List of participating countries \(HE\) V2.9 – 21.03.2025](#). Please refer to this document if you have any doubts as to your eligibility for funding.

3.1 Fellowship timeline

It is important to note that the fellowship timeline needs to be aligned with the fellowship application; **the earliest possible start date of the fellowship is the application creation date on the Trust-Grants™ platform**. In this sense, **it is possible to set a start date for the fellowship that occurs before the announcement of the evaluation process results**. All fellowships have to respect the maximum duration of the contributions as defined in table xx.

As for SM applicants, the fellowship timeline will have to be adapted to the scale and timing of the Standardisation Meeting – still respecting the maximum duration of 6 Months.

4. Eligible costs

Applicants shall provide a clear, well-justified and detailed description of the eligible costs in their applications. These can include:

- ▣ Personal Working Effort (this cannot exceed the EU maximum daily rate of 450 Euro)
- ▣ Travel costs
- ▣ Event registration fee(s)
- ▣ Membership fee(s) for SDO & SSO organisations

If your standardisation activity is partially covered by other resources, the items or activities already funded are not eligible for funding under the [StandICT.eu](#) 2029 fellowship.

Successful applicants will receive an email from Trust-IT Services, responsible for the financial management of StandICT 2029, with instructions and the necessary paperwork. Further details about financial aspects can be found in 'Guidelines for the Funded Fellows', in this document.

5. Criteria for evaluation

The initial eligibility screening will be undertaken by the Consortium to assess compliance to the call. Proposals which are ineligible for any reason or which do not meet the call criteria will be identified as such, and the applicant will receive an automatic notification from the system.

The consortium will consolidate all eligible proposals and submit them to the external evaluators (selected from the External Pool of Evaluators – EPE) to undertake the formal evaluation.

For being considered eligible, each proposal will have to respect the following conditions:

- ▣ The application must be complete in all its sections.
- ▣ The applicant must be an individual residing in the European Member States and Associate Countries (you can check them [here](#))
- ▣ An updated version of the CV must be uploaded

Each proposal will be evaluated on the basis of the following four criteria principle:

- ▣ Criterion 1 – Excellence - Focus: Quality, clarity, and necessity of the proposed activity, technical soundness, and understanding of the current standards landscape.
- ▣ Criterion 2 – Impact - Focus: Support to EU policy priorities in the ICT domain , alignment with ICT Rolling Plan topics, contribution to ICT standardisation, and leadership role in SDOs/Working Groups.
- ▣ Criterion 3 – Implementation - Focus: Feasibility, clarity, and realism of the plan, work structure, KPIs, and budget
- ▣ Criterion 4 – Inclusion & Knowledge Transfer - Focus: how the applicant promotes inclusion and knowledge sharing in ICT standardisation.

Scores will range from 1 to 10. The final scoring and ranking will be automatically determined by averaging the scores provided by the three independent members of the External Pool of Evaluators. All criteria have an equal weighting of 25% each

In the event of a tie between two or more proposals, where the allocated budget for a specific call does not allow funding for all, the proposal bearing the earliest time stamp of submission will be eligible for funding in the specific call.

Notes for chairs and convenors

If you are applying for [StandICT.eu](#) 2029 Open Calls and your role in the Working Groups is Chair/co-Chair or Convenor/Co-convenor, it is important to underline:

- ▣ the activities related to your role;
- ▣ the strategic relevance that chairs and convenors have, in particular for the activities that are continuous;
- ▣ For continuous activities: the progress made in between one application and the other.

6. Open call topics

The series of 6 Open Calls focus on the macro-areas of the key orientations of the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation³. Applications that address any of the topics mentioned below taken from the Multi-Stakeholder Platform Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation will be considered of equal validity and merit during the evaluation process.

▣ FOUNDATIONAL DRIVERS

- ▣ FOUNDATIONAL DRIVERS - Data economy
- ▣ FOUNDATIONAL DRIVERS - Cybersecurity / network and information security
- ▣ FOUNDATIONAL DRIVERS - ePrivacy

▣ KEY ENABLERS

- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - 5G and beyond
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Cloud and edge computing
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Data interoperability
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Internet of Things
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Electronic identification and trust services including e-signatures
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - e-Infrastructures for data and computing intensive science and the European Open Science Cloud
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Broadband infrastructure mapping
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Accessibility of ICT products and services
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Artificial Intelligence
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - European Global Navigation Satellite System (EGNSS)
- ▣ KEY ENABLERS - Quantum Technologies

▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Digital health, healthy living and ageing
- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Digital skills
- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Digital learning
- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - eGovernment
- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - eCall
- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Pandemic preparedness
- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Safety, transparency and due process online
- ▣ SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Emergency communications and public warning systems

3 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation>

INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET

- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - e-Procurement – pre- and post award
- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - e-Invoicing
- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - Retail Payments
- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - Preservation of digital cinema
- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - Fintech and Regtech Standardisation
- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - Blockchain and Distributed Digital Ledger Technologies
- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - Web 4.0 and virtual worlds
- INNOVATION FOR THE DIGITAL SINGLE MARKET - Media

SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Smart grids and smart metering
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Smart and sustainable cities and communities
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - ICT Environmental impact
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - European Electronic Toll Service (EETS)
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Intelligent Transport Systems - Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (ITS-CCAM) and Electromobility
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Digitisation of European Industry
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Robotics and autonomous systems
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Construction - building information modelling
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Water Management Digitalisation
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Single European Sky
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - U-space
- SUSTAINABLE GROWTH - Circular economy and sustainability

7. How to apply

The platform is available on the StandICT.eu 2029 website: [TRUST-GRANTS™](https://StandICT.eu).

Applicants who already applied for previous editions in 2026 and 2023 can **log in** with the old credentials.

StandICT.eu

About Open Calls Results Academy News & Events Beyond Grants Platform

Log in Create new account Reset your password

Log in

Username *

Password *

Log in

New applicants will have to first **create a new account**, and then once registered they can access the application form.

StandICT.eu

About Open Calls Results Academy News & Events Beyond Grants Platform

Log in Create new account Reset your password

Create new account

Email address *

The email address is not made public. It will only be used if you need to be contacted about your account or for opted-in notifications.

Username *

Several special characters are allowed, including space, period (.), hyphen (-), apostrophe ('), underscore (_), and the @ sign.

Password *

Password strength:

Confirm password *

Applicants must then fill in the application form with the required information.

The application can also be saved into draft and modified anytime until the closing date of the open call.

It is strongly recommended **not to wait until the last minute for submitting the final version of the application**, in order to avoid eventual technical issues which may not submit the proposal on time.

Once the application has been successfully submitted, applicants will be notified with an email from notification@standict.eu.

B. Guidance for the Funded Fellows

Financial aspects

The **grant is a lump sum**, meaning that it does not require timesheets or justifications (e.g., invoices) for costs.

Applicants will receive an automatic email with an update on their payment status from TRUST-GRANTS™ platform. This email **is not to be considered an indicator of a deadline for payment**. Trust-IT Services will follow up and start processing payments at the end of the fellowship based on the delivered and validated results as defined in the fellow's application form.

For fellows who request a prepayment, a valid justification linked to a milestone (for instance, the submission of the interim report) in addition to evidence of their early request (for instance, proof of travel expenses) must be provided to receive this prepayment

This payment process takes from 2 to 5 weeks to be completed. Subsequently, fellows will be informed that their payment will be transferred in the next 5 to 7 working days.

Applicants who supply their paperwork as a company (rather than as individuals) will be required to provide extra paperwork to register the company. This will mean that the payment for their grant will take longer to be received.

Information about taxes related to the funding

The financial contribution is a gross amount provided without deduction of any taxes or other duties which may be liable for payment in accordance with national tax regulations in your country of fiscal residence, should this count as income. Therefore, you should consult your local tax authority or accountant as to whether any taxes or other duties apply to the funding received. StandICT.eu 2029 cannot assume any liability, charge, responsibility or lien for paying any taxes or duties on the third-party funding provided, which lies solely with the fellow.

Monitoring of the funded fellows

The fellows perform all their reporting via [TRUST-GRANTS™](#), respecting the set deadlines. In this platform, the same profile and credentials are used as in the application phase. The funded fellow's dashboard has a dedicated section for drafting and submitting reports online. Additionally, the StandICT.eu admin team provides ongoing email support for all administrative matters related to the fellowship progress.

The reporting aims to understand the short-term impact of your fellowship contributions on the European ICT standards community, especially the European Commission and the Multi-Stakeholder Platform for ICT Standardisation, and to share your fellowship story with the StandICT.eu stakeholders:

- ▣ **For long-term fellowships**, fellows are required to submit two reports: an interim report (submitted at the midpoint of the activity) and a final report (submitted at the conclusion of the activity).
- ▣ **For short-term fellowships and organisation of standardisation meetings**, only the final report is required (at the end of the activity).

The report is structured into two parts: Section 1 gathers questions focusing on the profile of the funded expert and their background in ICT standardisation, while Section 2 is dedicated to the funded fellowship activity, its tangible results, and the resulting impact in the ICT standardisation arena.

The Interim Report enables tracking the mid-term progress of the fellowships, allowing for verification that the fellowship is progressing as planned and if any challenges or changes in the activity are encountered. It also helps the [StandICT.eu](#) team to gather the first key information of the activities, including the addressed standardisation items and processes, that can be disseminated to the [StandICT.eu](#) community.

The Final Report, submitted at the end of all funded fellowships, contains questions regarding the activities achieved, their impact on SMEs and on society and recommendations to continue (or not) with the activity beyond the fellowship duration.

Dissemination of the funded fellowship and acknowledgement of funding

Dissemination

The European Union funds the StandICT.eu 2029 project and its beneficiaries, so it is crucial to disseminate all achieved activities and obtain results related to the programme. This dissemination is done not only by the StandICT.eu project team but also by the funded fellows.

The funded fellows' work, and results are shared via different StandICT.eu channels, including:

- ▣ **New EUOS Repository:** The repository displays the reference of each standard and the profile of the fellow working on it, with links where available.
- ▣ **StandICT.eu Website:** The profiles of all funded fellows are published on a dedicated page⁴ of the project's website.
- ▣ **Social media: Fellows are asked to promote their funded contributions and activities on social media** (LinkedIn and X) by tagging StandICT.eu.
- ▣ **Success stories**⁵: All funded fellows can submit a success story presenting a standardisation activity that has been successfully finalised (these can be external to the StandICT.eu fellowship programme).

Useful contacts

Grants information and management:

m.giuffrida@trust-it-services.com

t.ridolfi@trust-it-services.com

Administration and financial management:

n.fracassi@trust-it-services.com

Fellowship information and guidance:

mona@australo.org

Mentorship programme information:

g.casalini@digitalsme.eu

⁴ <https://www.standict.eu/funded-fellows>

⁵ <https://www.standict.eu/success-stories>

Acknowledgement of EU-funding

Even more importantly, the funded fellows must acknowledge the European funding, especially in any scientific or academic publications directly related to the funded activity.

Example of the funding acknowledgement to be used in all publications

<p>Funded by the European Union</p>	<p>This activity is a beneficiary of EU funding via StandICT.eu 2029 Programme. StandICT.eu 2029 has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No. 101213612.</p>
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StandICT.eu 2029 Mentorship Programme

The **StandICT.eu Mentorship Programme** is open to all experts interested in developing or strengthening their engagement in ICT standardisation, whether as mentors or mentees. The programme connects experienced standardisation practitioners with newcomers or professionals wishing to deepen their understanding of standardisation processes, creating a supportive environment for knowledge exchange across different areas of expertise. The programme has the objective to complement the selection process, without being limited to funded StandICT Fellows.

The Mentorship Programme is designed to help new or less experienced experts engage effectively in the work of Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs) by providing guidance, practical insights, and personalised support from seasoned professionals. At the same time, it enables experienced experts to share their knowledge with the next generation of European standardisation contributors, helping to ensure that the EU maintains a strong, sustainable, and continuously growing standardisation knowledge base.

Actively participating in the StandICT Mentorship Programme will not only provide positive benefits for both mentors and mentees in terms of growth, learning, and networking, but, upon successful completion, their efforts will also be recognised within the **evaluation process** for the selection during StandICT Open Calls. Both mentors and mentees successfully participating under StandICT2029 mentorship programmes and fully completing the envisioned steps will receive additional bonus points that will positively influence and boost their overall evaluation score.

Please note that, for those who participated in past editions of the mentorship programme, these efforts will be recognised with the corresponding bonus points **only for Open Call 1**. From **Open Call 2 onwards**, experts who wish to continue benefiting from this recognition will need to participate again in the programme, which will be further structured under StandICT2029.

For more information about the mentorship programme, visit our webpage:

<https://standict.eu/mentorship-programme>

StandICT.eu2029

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 [/company/standict-eu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/standict-eu)

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